
Energy Management Strategies for Smart Infrastructure

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ABSTRACT

Article Info: Received: 30 November 2014 | Accepted: 21 January 2015 | Published online: 02 February 2015

Keywords: Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP), micro-grids, power management, renewable energy sources (RES).

The continuous growth of electricity demand and ever-increasing society awareness of climate change issues directly affect the development of the electrical power systems. The adaptation of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) offers reduction to the gas emissions produced by the electricity production from fossil-fuel power generation but also causes vulnerability to the power system. Recent technologies can be embraced to enhance the robustness of electricity supply in critical buildings. This paper proposes a method which uses an advanced control scheme for enhancing the operation of the critical building micro-grid during power-cut by utilizing the RES production. The method offers two different power management strategies (depending on the expected power system recovery time) for a resilient hospital micro-grid that includes RES; achieving longest autonomy of the micro-grid in island mode, or maximizing the load served within the micro-grid. The proposed method will be verified by simulation and selected results will be presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main objectives of this work is the utilization of the Renewable Energy Systems (RES) in micro-grid, which feeds one or more critical buildings. Two power management strategies are also studied for the micro-grid that can be benefit by maximum autonomy time and maximum load served during islanded operation. The resilience of the micro-grid is considered as priority of the study.

A micro-grid is a cluster of electrical loads with intelligent central management and the ability to operate on power utility mode and/or island mode. Unintentional islanding can result in power quality problems, serious equipment damage, and even safety from hazards to utility operation personnel. Therefore, a modern micro-grid requires active and passive algorithms that can be used for islanding detection [1], [2]. This is conventionally achieved by the inverter(s) of RES, however, this paper proposes the Smart Hospital Controller (SHC).

The design and operation of a future electrical power system requires refinement to achieve resilience [3]. The management strategy requires further development when a critical building/load is contained within micro-grid. In the literature, there are major developments in control of power converters in AC micro-grids [4]. Advance techniques for controlling the synchronization of RES to the micro-grid have also been developed [5]. The management of variable sources of power generation and consumption is challenging and requires the involvement of not only the state-of-the-art technologies but also of the consumers [6]. Accordingly, the proposed method offers a solution that automatically prioritizes the loads according to their criticality. Therefore, the most critical loads assure uninterrupted power supply.

Despite the fact that the power system (which used to be hierarchically and unidirectional controlled), the RES (on both the distribution and the transmission grids), and communication between them (which requires not only physical but also cyber security) are nowadays assumed linked, the quality of service and power stability are actively controlled for local and global objectives [7]. This increases the complexity of the dependencies and proves the necessity of enhanced control strategies. Though [7] emphasises the importance of a main swathe between the micro-grid and the main power line, this paper also proposes load management strategies for better control of distributed generation.

Although the power systems were originally designed for local power supply needs, now are expanding beyond state borders and the power system is assumed a part of larger system [8]. According to the European Commission (EC) preparedness planning, the relevant equipment for ideal configuration on emergency management [9] requires a back-up power, with alternative solutions if the main electricity supply fails. The proposed strategy satisfies the requirements of the EC. The two strategies provide optimized balance between the maximum load served and the longest power supply autonomy for critical loads. These results are achieved by pre-defining the criticality level of the micro-grid loads.

The structure of this paper is as follows. The significance of the paper on next generation infrastructure design is documented in Section 2. The resilient micro-grid

architecture along with its smart controller and hospital load categories are thoroughly investigated in Section 3. The power management strategies for achieving significant benefits from RES utilization is analysed in Section 4. Section 5 provides the verification of the controller method and strategies. The conclusion of the paper is provided at the end.

2. ELIMINATING MICRO-GRID VULNERABILITIES

Is there a need to increase our interest about the protection and resilience of infrastructures? This interest is strongly related to initiatives, by several governments that from the end of the 90s recognised the relevance of the undisturbed functioning of CI for the wellbeing of their population [10]. According to the policy framework for climate and energy of the European Commission [11] the Member States of the EU need flexibility to choose policies that are best-matched to their national energy mix and preferences. Otherwise, the continuous increase of fossil fuel consumption will not only increase the greenhouse gas emissions, but will also affect the security of energy supply.

The 20-20-20 targets, which are set by [12] aim for a 20% reduction in the overall fossil fuel consumption by the year 2020, compared to 1990 levels. According to the European Distribution System Operators' association (EDSO), Smart grids are a prerequisite to achieving the EU's ambitious energy and climate objectives to 2020 and beyond. The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan) aims to accelerate the development and deployment of low-carbon technologies. The European Technology Platform for Electricity Networks of the Future encourages the technology research and development pathways for the smart grids sector. Advancements of information and communication technologies (ICT) cause infrastructure owners to augment current infrastructures with such ICT, [13]. However, the introduction of smart grid technologies will be accompanied with many unexpected situations, which require years of experience to deliver reliable improvements [14].

The transition period, of existing infrastructure to smart grid technology, is critical for emergency buildings/areas (such as hospitals, emergency/crisis management headquarters etc.) where the reliability is a major priority. The method, which is proposed in this paper, offers significant advantages to the existing infrastructure. It introduces a large degree of redundancy and protection while improving the energy efficiency. The proposed micro-grid is adoptable to the smart grid technologies and gives additional resilience to the next generation infrastructure concept, without compromising the efficiency of power consumption.

3. MICRO-GRID DESCRIPTION

This paper focuses on enhancing the operation of a resilient micro-grid for critical buildings. In particular, a large hospital is considered as a case study. This section describes the structure of the hospital micro-grid, its main components and the main power management technique.

3.1 Micro-grid architecture

It is critical to ensure the uninterruptible power supply in a hospital. If the electrical installation of the hospital is designed as a micro-grid, it offers the advantages of being capable for an inter-connected and an islanded operation. To achieve these advantages, a number of technologies is required:

- Battery Storage Systems (BSS),
- Diesel Generators (DG),
- inverter based RES (e.g., photovoltaic systems (PV) and Wind Turbine Systems (WTS)),
- flexible loads, and
- a central controller (Smart Hospital Controller).

The single line diagram of the architecture is shown in Figure 1. In such a micro-grid structure it is assumed that the SHC measures the power exchanged with the grid (P), the power produced by the RES (P), the power for charging (negative) or discharging (positive) the BSS (P), the power produced by the DG (P) and the power demand by the hospital loads (P). Further, it is assumed that hospital loads are flexible and can be controlled (on and off) by the SHC.

Figure 1. The main architecture of a hospital micro-grid

Figure 2. Hospital loads are divided to four levels of load criticality

3.2 Load Categories

The loads of the hospital are divided according to their criticality level, as presented in Figure 2. There are four levels of load criticality, having the equipment with primary significance (e.g., intensive care unit) to be fed by Level A and equipment with secondary significance (but still very important) to be fed by Level B. Level C is for less crucial loads but still important for the normal operation of the hospital and Level D is for the least critical loads that can postpone their operation. Level C and Level D are more flexible and are divided in N and M partitions (each partition can be turned on and off by the SHC), respectively, in order to achieve longest autonomy or maximize

the load served by the micro-grid. The total hospital load in respect to the energy sources of the micro-grid is characterized by the following equation.

$$P = P + P + P + P \quad (1)$$

The criticality levels are set according to the maximum installed capacity, e.g., Level A has maximum installed capacity P but the actual consumed power (P) is less when some equipment of Level A are not in use. Similar annotation has been used for the loads in each criticality level. The total hospital load with respect to the load criticality levels is characterized by the following equation:

$$P = P + P + (P + P + \dots P) + (P + P + \dots P) \quad (2)$$

3.3 Battery storage system

The Energy Capacity EC of the battery is chosen appropriately to satisfy the worstcase scenario:

$$EC \geq t \cdot P \quad (3)$$

The power range of the BSS inverter is represented by:

$$P \leq P \leq P \quad (4)$$

where P is the maximum charging power and P is the maximum discharging power.

According to the BSS technology for maximizing the battery lifetime, the charging power cannot be more than half of the discharging power.

$$P \leq \frac{P}{2} \quad (5)$$

Combining (3) and (5) into (4), the inverter of the BSS has the following range:

$$-P \leq P \leq P \quad (6)$$

3.4 DG and RES

For enabling the islanding and autonomous operation of the hospital micro-grid, at least a DG is required. The power ratings of the DG should be able to serve the loads within Level A, Level B and Level C (Section 2.2) in order to ensure the uninterrupted operation of the hospital during black-outs. Thus, the power-rating of the DG is given by:

$$P = P + P + \sum P \quad (7) \text{ where } i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

The DG is equipped with a fuel tank that gives to a hospital few hours of autonomy without refilling the tank.

For extending the power autonomy of the micro-grid it is useful to have some inverterbased RES. Thus, the distributed power produced by the RES can be very useful either for extending the autonomy of micro-grid or for maximizing the load served during black-outs (as it is presented in Section 3).

3.5 Micro-grid operation

The operational modes of the micro-grid are listed in Table I. In normal operation, the SHC operates in Mode 0. During Mode 0 the hospital is interconnected with the utility, P , and the produced power by the RES is directly injected into the grid, which is the standard practice in conventional grids. The total hospital load in respect to the energy sources of the micro-grid is characterized by the following equation:

$$LS = P + P + P + P = P + P \quad (8)$$

However, in case of power-cuts and Black-Outs (BO), the hospital micro-grid operation needs to be continued. Therefore, when the BO occurs (t) the SHC detects the power-cut and instantly turns-off the Grid-connection Relay in order to proceed with an islanding operation. Immediately, the SHC activates Mode 1. During Mode 1, the inverter of BSS provides power from the battery pack to the hospital demand (positive values of P while the battery pack discharges) in order to serve all the critical loads included in Level A (P). Mode 1 ends when the DG starts up (t).

$$LS = P = P + P \quad (9)$$

Then, from t until the t (the instant when the State of Charge (SoC) of the BSS returns to 100%) the SHC operates in Mode 2. During Mode 2, the DG is operating and the battery is charging (power flows from the GD to the BSS providing negative values of P). In this mode, the requirements of the SHC are to serve all loads included in Level A and Level B:

$$LS = P + P = P + P + P \quad (10) \text{ while } P \text{ has a negative value.}$$

Mode 3 is the interval from the moment t until the recovery of the power grid, t . During this period, the BSS is not charging or discharging and thus, the load is served mainly by the DG. The LS during Mode 3 is represented by:

$$LS = P + P + P = P + P \quad (11)$$

When the utility is recovered the micro-grid can safely return to interconnected mode (Mode 0).

Table I. Description of the operation modes of hospital micro-grid

Operation mode	Grid Condition	Micro-grid Operation	Starts	Ends	Comments
Mode 0	Healthy	Interconnected	-	-	Normal Operation
Mode 1	Black-out	Islanding	t	$t + t$	Time required for the start-up of the DG
Mode 2	Black-out	Islanding	$t + t$	$t + t + t$	Time required for charging the back-up BSS after the DG is connected
Mode 3	Black-out	Islanding	$t + t + t$	t	Time until grid is recovered
Mode 0	Healthy	Interconnected	t	-	Grid is recovered Normal Operation

4 Proposed Power Management Strategies

The SHC is designed to run in two power management strategies. The two strategies manage the use of the RES according to the needs of the hospital and the Black-out recovery time. Both strategies satisfy the requirements of Section 2.

One of the strategies offers the longest possible autonomy time for the micro-grid, which is very useful in cases when the recovery time of the black-out is unknown. The

second strategy offers maximum load served which reduces the impact of the blackout on the hospital services. The differences between the two strategies are listed in Table II. The strategies are not applied for Mode 1. During Mode 1 the RES (if they generate any power) are reducing the BSS discharging rate.

4.1 Strategy A for longest autonomy

The first power management strategy aims to achieve the longest autonomy possible during island mode. This strategy uses the power generated from RES to save the fuel of the DG. Therefore, the autonomy working time of the DG is extended. The autonomy extension is proportional to the generated P . This strategy is preferred when the power system recovery is unknown.

During Mode 2, strategy A ensures power supply in Level A and Level B. All power generated by RES is used to reduce the power consumption by the DG, and therefore, save some fuel. During Mode 3, strategy A ensures power supply in Level A, Level B and Level C. All power generated by RES is used to reduce the power consumption by the DG, and continue to save some fuel until the utility recovers from the black-out.

This strategy can save a substantial amount of fuel when the power generated from RES is sufficient and it is significant when the black-out lasts for several hours.

Table II. Description of the operation in each mode

Operation mode	BSS	DG	RES	Master	Load Served (LS)	Fuel Consumption
Mode 0	Fully Charged	Not used	P is injected into the grid	Grid	Normal Operation	-
Mode 1	Discharging to serve P	Starting up	P is used for serving the hospital loads	Inverter	$LS = P$	For starting-up the DG
Mode 2A	Charging	Operating	P is used for extending the autonomy of DG	DG	$LS = P + P$	For serving $P + P - P$
Mode 2B	Charging	Operating	P is used for serving extra hospital loads	DG	$LS = P + P + P$	For serving $P + P$
Mode 3A	Fully Charged	Operating	P is used for extending the autonomy of DG	DG	$LS = P + P + P$	For serving $P + P + P - P$

Mode 3B	Fully Charged	Operating	P is used for serving extra hospital loads	DG	$LS = P + P + P + P$	For serving $P + P + P$
Mode 0	Fully Charged	Not used	P is injected into the grid	Grid	Normal Operation	-

4.2 Strategy B for maximum load served

The second power management strategy aims to serve the maximum load possible during the islanding mode. The idea of the strategy is to use the power generated from RES to serve additional loads within the micro-grid. This strategy is applied once the recovery time of the power system is known and the fuel of the GD sufficient until the recovery.

During Mode 2, strategy B ensures power supply in Level A and Level B. The power generated by RES is used to support additional loads from partitions of Level C (e.g., P , P etc.). Therefore, even when the BSS absorbs power (to charge the battery unit) SHC provides power to Level C. During Mode 3, strategy B ensures power supply in Level A, Level B and Level C. The power generated by RES is used to support additional loads from partitions of Level D (e.g., P , P etc.). Therefore, when RES generate full power, the SHC can provide power to even supply Level D.

5 Method Verification

The resilient Micro-grid method of Smart Hospital Controller described in Section 2 and the power management strategies described in Section 3 have been investigated using a simulation model in MATLAB. The model uses the values of Table III.

This section provides the results of the micro-grid powers in three cases during blackout. The study covers the graph lines of following values during the four modes:

- Power demand by the hospital,
- Power consumed by the hospital loads,
- Power supplied by the grid,
- Power supplied by the BSS,
- Power generated by the DG, and □ Power generated by the RES.

Table III. Design data of the test-bed simulated micro-grid

System	Data
RES	$P = 30$ kW connected through an inverter During simulation □ $43\% < P < 83\%$

DG	150 kW, Fuel Tank for 6-hour autonomy with a Diversity Factor (DF) equal to 50%
BSS	$P_{max} = 50 \text{ kW}$, $P_{min} = 25 \text{ kW}$, $EC = 12.5 \text{ kWh}$
Installed capacity of Hospital Loads	$P_1 = 50 \text{ kW}$, $P_2 = 75 \text{ kW}$, $P_3 = 3 \text{ kW}$, $P_4 = 4 \text{ kW}$, $P_5 = 5 \text{ kW}$, $P_6 = 6 \text{ kW}$, $P_7 = 7 \text{ kW}$, $P_8 = 12 \text{ kW}$, $P_9 = 15 \text{ kW}$, $P_{10} = 18 \text{ kW}$, $P_{11} = 21 \text{ kW}$, $P_{12} = 24 \text{ kW}$.
Diversity Factor (DF) of Hospital Loads	$DF_1 = 0.6 \pm 0.2$, $DF_2 = 0.65 \pm 0.15$, $DF_3 = 0.7 \pm 0.1$, $DF_4 = 0.625 \pm 0.125$, $DF_5 = 0.525 \pm 0.075$, $DF_6 = 0.675 \pm 0.075$, $DF_7 = 0.375 \pm 0.025$, $DF_8 = 0.6 \pm 0.1$, $DF_9 = 0.525 \pm 0.125$, $DF_{10} = 0.4 \pm 0.1$, $DF_{11} = 0.525 \pm 0.075$, $DF_{12} = 0.4 \pm 0.05$.
Back-Out (BO) information	Black-Out (BO) occurs at $t = 5 \text{ min}$ Black-Out duration: 150 min

Figure 3. Hospital micro-grid operation when there is no RES production

Figure 4. Hospital micro-grid operation when there is a 30 kW installed RES and when the power management strategy A is followed for extending the autonomy of the micro-grid

5.1 BO during the absence of RES

The analysis of a BO incident has been done during the absence of RES. The graphical representation of the results is shown in Figure 3. The graphs verify that the SHC offers uninterruptible supply to Level A which includes all the critical loads. In Mode 2 the loads of Level B are supplied and the battery is charged. In Mode 3, all loads up to Level C are supplied until the recovery time of the BO.

The curve of the fuel while is consumed is also observed.

5.2 BO with strategy A

The analysis of strategy A has been done when a BO occurs while some RES. The graphical representation of the results is shown in Figure 4. In Mode 2 the loads of Level B are supplied, the battery is charged, and the RES support the DG to save fuel. In Mode 3, all loads up to Level C are supplied until the recovery time of the BO.

The fuel slope shows a significant reduction in fuel consumption.

Figure 5. Hospital micro-grid operation when

there is a 30 kW installed RES and when the power management strategy B is followed for maximizing the load served

5.3 BO with strategy B

The analysis of strategy B has been done when a BO occurs while some RES. The graphical representation of the results is shown in Figure 5. In Mode 2 the loads of Level B are supplied and some partitions of Level C are also supplied, and the battery has been charging. In Mode 3, all loads up to Level C and some partitions of Level D are supplied until the recovery time of the BO.

The curve of the load served is higher than the previous examples.

5.4 Summary of the results

The significance of the SHC and the two strategies are shown in Table IV. It is observed that strategy B serves the maximum load and that strategy A saves more fuel. It is also observed that the RES power support BSS to prevents large discharge of the battery units.

6 Conclusion

Without compromising the benefits of the Smart Grid technologies, this paper proposes a method to enhance the resilience and the efficiency of a Microgrid, towards the targets of the EU. The paper investigates a smart controller which measures and regulates the power demand of a critical building (using a hospital as case-study), the power consumed by the loads, the power supplied by the grid and by the battery system, and the power generated by the additional generator and by the RES.

The paper proposes two different power management strategies for a resilient hospital micro-grid, that includes RES. The proposed methods offer an advanced control scheme for enhancing the operation of the hospital micro-grid during power-cut by utilizing the RES production. Depending on the expected power system recovery time, the first strategy reaches extended autonomy of the micro-grid in island mode, while the second strategy served more electrical loads within the micro-grid. The proposed methods were verified by simulation results and selected results were presented.

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